

Trends in AI-generated content in The Lancet Regional Health commentaries, 2020–2025

Victor Mwangi^{1,2}

vmwanginjor@alumni.unav.es

Carlos Chaccour^{1*}

cchaccour@unav.es

¹Institute for Culture and Society-NCID Navarra Center for International Development,
Universidad de Navarra, Pamplona, Spain

²Strathmore Institute of Mathematical Sciences, Strathmore University, Nairobi, Kenya

*Correspondence to:

Institute for Culture and Society-NCID, Navarra Center for International Development,
Universidad de Navarra, Pamplona, Spain. cchaccour@unav.es.

Word count: 877

The dawn of Large Language Models (LLMs) and generative AI has transformed many sectors worldwide. In academia it is a fact that researchers and students are leveraging LLMs for writing manuscripts. Recent social commentary has expressed issues regarding how AI is altering how learning is understood and in general how universities function¹. Media reports have revealed a growing concern about AI-generated submissions in scientific correspondence and editorial processes². A recent report reveals how Pangram Labs used their AI detection software to analyze some 76,000 abstract submitted to an international conference and showed that at least one fifth of them were fully AI-generated and more than half had indications of AI³. We used Pangram to analyze close to 1,000 comments published by The Lancet regional Health Journals (TLRHJ) from the launch of the first journal in 2020 until December 2025, and describe the evolution of AI-generated content in them over the last six years.

Albeit short, comments in The Lancet journals are written by experts in their field and are often highly cited and influential when it comes to policy discussions. There are five regional journals, namely: Africa, Americas, Europe, South East Asia, and Western Pacific. The analysis covered 993 comments published between August 2020 and December 2025.

After populating a database with the metadata for each commentary, we used the Pangram AI detector ⁴ to analyze the articles' text. We obtained scores ranging from 0 to 100 reflecting the amount of human-written, AI-assisted or AI-generated content for each piece.

Figure 1 illustrates the evolution of AI-generated and AI-assisted comments in the Lancet Regional Health journals from 2020 to 2025. There were 359 comments published before the launch of ChatGPT (From August 2020 to November 2022), all were classified as fully human written.

Starting in 2023, 3.7% of the comments (7/185) contained some AI-generated or AI-assisted content. This proportion tripled in 2024 to 11.3% (23/203) and almost doubled again the following year to reach 20.9% (48/229) in 2025. The increment over this three-year period is almost six-fold. The AI-generated content in the TLRHJ comments in 2025 ranged from 4.5% (Europe) to 45% (Africa). We also calculated the year-to-year growth in the numbers of commentaries published, which was 9.73% for 2023-24 and 12.81% for 2024-25. However, if the AI-generated and AI-assisted comments are excluded, the growth is merely 1.12% and 0.56% respectively for each period.

Figure 1. Commentary publication trends across all The Lancet Regional Health journals (2020-2025). In the timeline above, the blue boxes indicate the date of the first Online-First publication for each journal. The orange boxes indicate the launch dates of major LLMs. In the bar graph below, each column is composed of stacked horizontal lines, one for each commentary published that year. The horizontal bars range from zero to 100 in terms of human-written content (green), AI-assisted content (yellow) and AI-generated content (red). The stacked graphs on the right display 2025 comments disaggregated by regional journal.

Additionally, we conducted an internal validation of the Pangram AI detector using the very same dataset of TLRHJ commentaries. We used a subset of 50 randomly selected commentaries published between 2020 and 2022, before the launch of any LLM (“original” column in **figure 2**). We then used ChatGPT 5.2 and Pangram as follows: (a) The first strategy was focused on identifying whether Pangram would categorize human written content that had been merely corrected using ChatGPT as either fully human, AI-generated or AI-assisted. This was done by giving ChatGPT the following prompt, “Given the following text, kindly improve its readability, flow, punctuation, grammar and do not add or remove any substantial part: <Insert Text>.” The “updated” version was then analyzed using Pangram. The results of this are shown in the “assisted” column in Figure 2. (b) The second strategy explored whether Pangram would misclassify AI-generated content as human written content. For this, the prompt given to ChatGPT was as follows, “Please pick out the main ideas of this comment: <Insert Text>. Using these ideas please write an 800–900-word piece and provide references.” The generated response was then analyzed using Pangram. The results are provided in the “generated” column in Figure 2.

Figure 1: Internal validation of the Pangram AI detection tool. The left panel shows the Pangram AI classification scores for 50 randomly selected comments published between 2020 and 2022, before the launch of any LLM. The “assisted” panel shows the AI classifications after ChatGPT revised the texts for readability, flow, grammar and punctuation. The “generated” panel on the right displays the AI classifications of 50 new comments generated by ChatGPT based on main ideas extracted from the original texts. The metrics provided on the right correspond to Pangram’s capacity to differentiate AI-generated from human-generated content, i.e. AI-assisted content was considered human in this analysis. LR: likelihood ratio, NPV: negative predictive value, PPV: positive predictive value, FPR: false positive rate, FNR: false negative rate.

Pangram reports training their AI detection model on approximately 3 million human-authored scientific papers from the pre-LLM era (pre-2021). Their validation claims an accuracy of 99% in a curated benchmark of 1,976 documents spanning different domains. Our internal validation using the TLRHJ dataset shows that Pangram, albeit not perfect, is accurate in detecting AI-generation while retaining a rate of zero false positives for human-written and even lightly AI-assisted text. Under these validation conditions, our estimates of AI-generated content are unlikely to reflect false positives in pre-LLM texts and may therefore represent conservative estimates.

This study provides evidence of an increasing role of LLMs and generative AI in scientific commentaries across all The Lancet Regional Health Journals. We document a clear upward trend

in the use of AI-generated and AI-assisted content in these publications. The growth of AI-generated content is rapid and accelerating. AI-classified comments account for a sizeable share of the net increase in commentary output during 2023–2025. On aggregate, the 2025 average AI-affiliated content score is 12.57%, which seems moderate but is not negligible and when disaggregated into the respective regions, the scores exhibit high heterogeneity, with TLRH Europe and TLRH South East Asia having combined generated/assisted scores below 9% while TLRH Africa, despite having the fewest commentaries published in 2025, was close to 50%. Of note, considering the rather small number of 2025 publications in some regional journals, these proportions should be interpreted cautiously.

The increasing integration of generative AI into scientific correspondence raises major concerns regarding authorship disclosure, transparency, and editorial standards. As journals adapt to this ever-evolving space, especially those with a strong influence in global policy, clear reporting norms and methodological accuracy in AI detection will be essential.

Declarations

Author contributions

Conceptualisation: VM, CCh

Methodology: VM, CCh,

Data curation: VM

Formal analysis: VM, CCh

Investigation: VM

Supervision: CCh

Writing - original draft: VM, CCh

Writing - review & editing: VM, CCh

Funding acquisition: NA

Declaration of interests

All authors declare no conflict of interest

Acknowledgements

The Pangram score of this manuscript is 100% human

Data sharing statement

All anonymized data relevant to this article will be publicly available [here](#). Anonymized pangram reports are available upon request.

References

- 1 Purser R. AI is Destroying the University and Learning Itself. *Curr Aff* 2025; published online Dec 1. <https://www.currentaffairs.org/news/ai-is-destroying-the-university-and-learning-itself> (accessed Feb 23, 2026).
- 2 Kolata G. The Editor Got a Letter From ‘Dr. B.S.’ So Did a Lot of Other Editors. *N. Y. Times*. 2025; published online Nov 4. <https://www.nytimes.com/2025/11/04/science/letters-to-the-editor-ai-chatbots.html> (accessed Feb 23, 2026).
- 3 Naddaf M. Major AI conference flooded with peer reviews written fully by AI. *Nature* 2025; **648**: 256–7.

4 Emi B, Spero M. Technical Report on the Pangram AI-Generated Text Classifier. 2024;
published online July 29. DOI:10.48550/arXiv.2402.14873.